

Climate change concerns of UNC students and their awareness of sustainability actions on campus

Authors of the report: Sydnee Klug¹, Kennedy Dechant¹, and Arika Virapongse²
Final draft completed on: March 8, 2024

Executive summary

The COOLER tabling event at the University Center (UC) of the University of Northern Colorado (UNC) aimed to gauge student perceptions of climate change and awareness of sustainability activities on campus while promoting engagement with the COOLER project. The event involved surveying participants on their concerns about climate change, their awareness of sustainable activities on campus, and their suggestions for future sustainability events.

Results indicated that the majority of respondents expressed concern or alarm about climate change, with many feeling uninformed or unsure about their level of concern. While awareness of sustainability activities on campus was limited, responses highlighted initiatives primarily driven by student groups such as Student LEAF and Earth Guardians. Suggestions for future events focused on areas like sustainable lighting, energy-efficient appliances, composting, and reusable food containers.

The tabling event was deemed successful for gathering valuable data for the COOLER project. Despite the limited engagement, attendees were friendly, indicating potential for further dialogue.

This study suggests that there is a need for increased education and awareness around climate change, as well as improved communication about existing sustainability initiatives on campus and continued dialogue on sustainability. It underscores the importance of student-led efforts in driving sustainability action at UNC.

Goals of the study

The goals for the COOLER tabling event at the University Center (UC) at University of Northern Colorado (UNC) were to connect with UNC students and gather information about how they felt about climate change, and what they know and think about sustainability activities on campus. The tabling event also aimed to inform attendees about the COOLER

¹ University of Northern Colorado

² Middle Path EcoSolutions, LLC

project, and provide a way for them to get more involved in the project and connect with others within the COOLER community, such as through social media.

Results

Perceptions on climate change

A total of 26 people participated in the climate change perceptions activity; more people engaged with the table co-hosts but did not all contribute to the activity. The majority of responses were from students at UNC, but a high school student, parent, and a staff member participated and wrote comments. The number of responses in each category and eleven additional comments are recorded in Table 1.

Table 1. Responses to Question 1 “How concerned do you feel about climate change and why?” (n=26).

Climate Concern Category:	Number of responses:	Responses with comment
Alarmed	6	
Concerned	14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It’s hot out here (student) • I’m concerned with the wasteful nature of our culture (parent) • Wish there was more I could do (student) • Run for the hills, the coast will be gone (student) • I blame the corporatist autocrats in charge of the government (student) • In the middle of cautious and concerned (student)
Cautious	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aware (highschool student) • Not worried at all, but it’s for sure a problem (student)
Disengaged	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many ideas aren’t explored enough (student)
Doubtful	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change happens every spring, summer, winter, and fall (staff)
Dismissive	0	
Other	1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uninformed (student)
Total:	26	11

Sustainable activities and events on campus

For Question 2 “Are you aware of any sustainable activities on campus?”, six people wrote responses (Figure 1). The written responses were:

- ★ Waste not
- ★ Thrift pop-up
- ★ Student LEAF
- ★ Earth Guardians
- ★ Water stations for reusable water bottles
- ★ Changed some on campus lighting to LED from fluorescent, big ass fans, and the solar flower – (Student LEAF)

Figure 1. Responses to Question 2 “Are you aware of any sustainable activities on campus?”.

For Question 3 “What type of sustainable events/activities does UNC need?”, there were five responses (Figure 2). The written responses were:

- ★ Sustainable lighting
- ★ Energy efficient appliances in the dining hall

- ★ Composting (n=3; underlining indicated agreement by another person)
- ★ Sustainable lawn care/native grass species
- ★ Reusable food containers in the UC

Figure 2. Responses to Question 3 “What type of sustainable events/activities does UNC need?”.

Discussion

For Question 1, the majority of the 26 respondents surveyed were “concerned” about climate change (53.8%), while the next largest group of respondents stated that they were “alarmed” (23.1%). However, many of the people we spoke with seemed unsure of their “climate concern category”. Some respondents mentioned to the co-hosts that they felt uninformed or unaware; these comments were not formally recorded as responses. This is an important note to consider as COOLER moves forward with student engagement. Rather than focusing on how to get students to talk about climate change, we would recommend introducing an initial step to inform students about climate change.

Some people verbally expanded on the responses that they contributed via the sticky note, as well offered suggestions about the COOLER mission.

There were only six responses to Question 2. Both co-hosts were actively involved with sustainability activities on UNC campus at the time of the study, and they

agreed that the six responses covered all of the activities that they themselves were aware of. While it is possible that there are other sustainability activities on campus, this result could be due to the relatively small number of sustainable practices at the university, or to a lack of advertising and communication about UNC's other sustainable programs. It could also imply that the sustainability programs that UNC does have are advertised well. The responses referred to activities that are related to Student LEAF (Student Leadership for Environmental Action Fund) or Earth Guardians³, which are both student groups at UNC. Some of the respondents were from these two groups, which could be another possibility as to why the responses reflected what these two groups offer.

Question 3 had five responses that we believe are all actionable ideas for UNC. All of the listed ideas are in progress or current discussion items for UNC's Student LEAF.

Results from both questions suggest that sustainability actions on campus are led mainly by student-led groups, rather than by University administrators.

The results were largely expected, although we had hoped that more people would want to converse longer about the topic. All of the attendees were very friendly while speaking to the co-hosts at the table, but they also seemed hesitant to engage—possibly because they were approaching a table that was asking them to actively participate in an activity. Some hesitation might have also stemmed from the perception that climate change is a hot topic that is being politicized.

Conclusions of the study

The majority of respondents stated that they were “concerned” or “alarmed” about climate change. Respondents showed good awareness of the sustainability activities that were occurring on campus. All of the responses about current sustainability activities and potential new activities were related to current student activities/discussion. Students appear to be motivated and effective at leading sustainability action at UNC.

This was the first tabling event that was conducted as part of the COOLER project. We believe that it was a successful approach for reaching UNC students and getting data about their perceptions around climate change.

Moving forward with future tabling events we recommend introducing a new activity that informs students about climate change, and asking: (1) Are students aware of any sustainability/climate change issues/activities on campus? And (2) What type of events or activities would get people to talk more about sustainability/climate change or to take more action?

³ Associated with Earth Guardians International

Methods of the study

COOLER staff set up a table at the University Center (UC) by the food court to talk to students about COOLER and climate change perceptions. The table was set up and co-hosted by two COOLER staff (authors SK and KD) from 11:00 am to 1:00 pm (2 hours) on February 19th, 2024. This time was selected to coincide with the lunch period when more people would be around. Additionally, the date was an orientation day, so prospective students and parents were able to visit the table.

Figure 3. Photo of the table, some written responses from attendees, and the table co-hosts (authors SK and KD).

At the table, we asked 3 survey questions. The first question aimed to understand how attendees felt about climate change. The second question aimed to see what sustainable events/actions on campus they were aware of. The third question asked people about what types of sustainable events/actions on campus that they would like to see.

To bring people to the table, one co-host approached people passing by and asked: “Do you have a second?” Then the survey questions were asked. As an incentive, people who participated in the survey were offered stickers or candy after they had answered the questions. It is also worth noting that some of the participants stopped at the table because they knew one of or both of the team members running the table.

Perceptions on climate change (primary question)

Six climate change emotions have been identified by the Yale Program on Climate Change Communication’s project on Global Warming’s Six Americas⁴. These emotions are: Alarmed, Concerned, Cautious, Disengaged, Doubtful, or Dismissive. A Global Warming’s Six Americas artwork (Figure 4) pairs each emotion with a small graphic. For our study, this artwork was printed on an 8.5 x 11 inch sheet of white printer paper to use as a data collection tool.

To capture their perceptions around climate change, attendees were asked to use the printed artwork to choose one of six emotions for their feelings about climate change. Attendees were asked to place a sticky note near the emotion that resonated most with them. It was optional to include an explanation about why they felt that way, but some participants found it helpful to explain their choice because they felt that one word did not sufficiently capture their feelings about climate change. Adding a sticky note was optional to anyone who visited the table; the activity was not limited to just students, although students were the target audience.

⁴ Yale Program on Climate Change Communication (2023) Global Warming’s Six Americas. <https://climatecommunication.yale.edu/about/projects/global-warmings-six-americas/>

Figure 4. Global Warming's Six Americas. Artwork by Michael Sloan.

Sustainable actions/events on campus (secondary questions)

If table attendees were willing to participate longer, they were asked to respond to two prompts written on two paper pads. Participants could choose to answer both, just one, or neither. Question 2 was “*Are you aware of any sustainable activities on campus?*”. Question 3 was “*What type of sustainable events/activities does UNC need?*”. Again, students were the target audience, but anyone was welcomed to respond to the prompts. Participants wrote their ideas on a large-format paper that was prepared for the purpose of capturing their ideas. If there was an idea already written that another person agreed with, an underline was added.

About the study

The study was conducted as part of the COOLER project (COmmunity COllaboration and LEarning for climate Resilience), which is an NSF-funded initiative (award #2228170) aimed at developing a learning ecosystem in Northern Colorado to strengthen climate change resilience. All of the authors were paid as staff on the COOLER project.

The data collection protocol (protocol #2207041159) for this study was reviewed and determined to be exempt by the Institutional Review Board at University of Northern Colorado.